

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

SYNTHESIS AND PHYSICAL-CHEMICAL STUDY OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS IN THE $\text{TlAs}_2\text{Se}_4\text{-CuCr}_2\text{Te}_4$ SYSTEM

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Abstract

In the $\text{TlAs}_2\text{Se}_4\text{-CuCr}_2\text{Te}_4$ system, samples were synthesized in a wide range and studied by methods of physical and chemical analysis: differential thermal analysis (DTA), X-ray diffraction analysis (XRD), microstructural analysis (MSA), as well as determination of density and microhardness and its was constructed T-x phase diagram. It has been established that the phase diagram of the $\text{TlAs}_2\text{Se}_4\text{-CuCr}_2\text{Te}_4$ system is quasi-binary and eutectic. The composition of the eutectic formed between the compounds TlAs_2Se_4 and CuCr_2Te_4 is 10 mol % CuCr_2Te_4 , temperature 498 K. At room temperature, solid solutions based on TlAs_2Se_4 in the system reach 3 mol. % CuCr_2Te_4 , and based on CuCr_2Te_4 – 7 mol % TlAs_2Se_4 . Under normal conditions, the glass transition region based on CuCr_2Te_4 extends to 12 mol % TlAs_2Se_4 .

Keywords: system, quasi-binary, eutectic, microhardness, solidus, phase diagram

Introduction

When synthesizing the components TlAs_2Se_4 and CuCr_2Te_4 of the $\text{TlAs}_2\text{Se}_4\text{-CuCr}_2\text{Te}_4$ system, the compounds As_2Se_3 , TlSe , CuTe and Cr_2Te_3 were used. Let us characterize these compounds separately. The As_2Se_3 compound is a photosensitive material obtained in the form of glass under ordinary conditions and is widely used in the optical industry [1-6]. Chalcogenide fiber based on As_2S_3 and As_2Se_3 compounds has found application as a compact nonlinear medium providing effective Romanov amplification and generation, pulse compression, optical regeneration, and wavelength conversion [7-10]. The TlSe compound and its ternary compounds are also photosensitive materials [11,12]. The spinel-type compound CuCr_2Te_4 , obtained by the chemical interaction of CuSe and Cr_2Te_3 compounds, is a ferromagnetic material [13,14]. From this point of view, materials with magneto-optical properties can also be alloys of complex composition obtained through the chemical interaction of the compounds TlAs_2Se_4 and CuCr_2Te_4 . A number of systems involving thallium chalcogenides have been studied in the literature [15-19].

The TlAs_2Se_4 compound melts at 563 K with an open maximum and crystallizes in the tetragonal syngony, lattice parameters: $a = 10.52$; $c = 8.85$ Å; $z = 6$, $\rho_{\text{pucn.}} = 6.72$ g/cm³; $\rho_{\text{X-ray}} = 6.81$ g/cm³ [20]. The CuCr_2Te_4 compound melts congruently at 1428 K and crystallizes in the cubic syngony, lattice parameter: $a = 11.134$ Å [21]. The CuCr_2Te_4 compound undergoes a phase transition at a temperature of 1083 K.

Experimental part

Alloys of the $\text{TlAs}_2\text{Se}_4\text{-CuCr}_2\text{Te}_4$ system were synthesized from the TlAs_2Se_4 and CuCr_2Te_4 components in evacuated quartz ampoules at a pressure of 0.133 Pa in the temperature range 770-1470 K.. The resulting alloys were subjected to heat treatment at 503 K for 300 h for their homogenization. Then the alloys of the system were studied by DTA, X-ray diffraction

analysis, MSA, density and microhardness measurements.

Differential thermal analysis was carried out using a TERMOSCAN-2 device. Chromel-alumel was used as a thermocouple. The heating rate was 5 K/min. X-ray phase analysis of the alloys was carried out on a D2 PHASER X-ray diffractometer. A $\text{CuK}\alpha$ electrode was used as an irradiator. Microhardness was measured using a PMT-3 metallographic microscope. Microstructure analysis was carried out using a MIM-8 microscope. When determining the densities of the system alloys, the pycnometric method was used and toluene was used as a filler.

Results and its discussion

Alloys of the $\text{TlAs}_2\text{Se}_4\text{-CuCr}_2\text{Te}_4$ system are black substances obtained in compact form. During the differential thermal analysis of the alloys, it was established that two and three endothermic effects were obtained in the thermograms of the samples. On thermograms of alloys in the range of 0-12 mol % CuCr_2Te_4 in the system, a softening temperature characteristic of glasses is observed at $T_g = 428$ K.

When studying the microstructure of alloys of the $\text{TlAs}_2\text{Se}_4\text{-CuCr}_2\text{Te}_4$ system, it was found that single-phase alloys are formed around the main components of the system.

To determine the accuracy of the results of microstructural and differential thermal analysis, X-ray phase analysis of alloys containing 5, 10, 70 and 93 mol % CuCr_2Te_4 (Fig. 1).

As a result, it was discovered that there were no diffraction lines in the diffraction patterns of samples with concentrations of 5 and 10 mol % CuCr_2Te_4 . This indicates that these samples are glassy. The diffraction lines present in the diffraction patterns of the 70 mol % CuCr_2Te_4 sample are a mixture of diffraction lines of the TlAs_2Se_4 and CuCr_2Te_4 compounds, that is, the sample is two-phase. X-ray diffraction pattern of sample 93 mol % CuCr_2Te_4 is identical to the X-ray diffraction pattern of the CuCr_2Te_4 compound. This sample is

a solid solution alloy based on the CuCr_2Te_4 compound. The T-x phase diagram of the TlAs_2Se_4 - CuCr_2Te_4 system was constructed based on the results of physical and chemical analysis methods (Fig. 2). The phase diagram of the TlAs_2Se_4 - CuCr_2Te_4 system is a quasi-binary section of the quasi-ternary system TlAs_2Se_4 -

$\text{CuTe-Cr}_2\text{Te}_3$. In the system at room temperature, solid solutions based on TlAs_2Se_4 are equal to 3 mol % CuCr_2Te_4 , and based on the compound CuCr_2Te_4 - 7 mol % TlAs_2Se_4 .

Fig.1. Diffraction patterns of alloys of the TlAs_2Se_4 - CuCr_2Te_4 system. 1- TlAs_2Se_4 , 2-5, 3-10, 4-70, 5-93, 6-100 mol % CuCr_2Te_4 .

Fig.2. T-x phase diagram of the TlAs_2Se_4 - CuCr_2Te_4 system.

The $TlAs_2Se_4$ component of the $TlAs_2Se_4$ - $CuCr_2Te_4$ system has the form of glass and participates in the system as a glass former. During normal cooling, glass-forming regions are formed based on the $TlAs_2Se_4$ compound, extending up to 12 mol % $CuCr_2Te_4$.

The liquidus of the system consists of the primary crystallization curves of a δ -solid solution based on the $TlAs_2Se_4$ compound and an α -solid solution based on the $CuCr_2Te_4$ compound. Cocrystallization of the compounds $TlAs_2Se_4$ and $CuCr_2Te_4$ ends at the double eutectic point, coordinate 10 mol % $CuCr_2Te_4$, temperature 498°C. Two-phase alloys consisting of ($\delta+\alpha$) crystallize below the solidus line in the system.

When measuring the microhardness of alloys of the $TlAs_2Se_4$ - $CuCr_2Te_4$ system, two different values were obtained. The dependence of the microhardness and density of the alloys of the $TlAs_2Se_4$ - $CuCr_2Te_4$ system on the composition is given in Table 1. As a result of measuring the microhardness of the alloys, two different values were found. The microhardness of the δ -solid solution obtained based on the $TlAs_2Se_4$ compound varies within the range (1100-1250) MPa. The microhardness of α -solid solutions based on the $CuCr_2Te_4$ compound varies within the range (1850-1870) MPa.

Table 1.

Compositions, DTA results, measurements of microhardness and density of of the $TlAs_2Se_4$ - $CuCr_2Te_4$ system

Composition, mol %		Thermal effects, K	S_{thlq} , q/sm ³	Microhardness, MPa	
$TlAs_2Se_4$	$CuCr_2Te_4$			δ	α
				P=0,10 N	P=0,15 N
100	0.0	563	6,45	1100	–
97	3,0	523,553	6,46	1150	–
95	5,0	503,548	6,47	1200	–
90	10	498	6,47	Eutek.	Eutek.
80	20	498,793	6,47	–	–
70	30	498,793,1023	6,47	–	1870
60	40	498,793,1143	6,47	–	1870
50	50	498,793,1223	6,48	–	1870
40	60	498,793,1293	6,49	–	1870
30	70	498,793,1333	6,49	–	1870
20	80	498,793,1373	6,50	–	1870
10	90	498,848,1403	6,54	–	1870
5,0	95	1013,1273,1423	6,53	–	1860
0,0	100	1083, 1428	6,51	–	1850

Conclusion

After the synthesis of composite alloys of the $TlAs_2Se_4$ - $CuCr_2Te_4$ system, its T-x phase diagram was constructed by studying the methods of physicochemical analysis. The phase diagram of the system is quasibinary, eutectic type. Cocrystallization of the compounds $TlAs_2Se_4$ and $CuCr_2Te_4$ ends at the eutectic point, composition 10 mol % $CuCr_2Te_4$, temperature 498 K. In the system at room temperature, solid solutions based on the $TlAs_2Se_4$ compound reach 3 mol % $CuCr_2Te_4$, and based on the $CuCr_2Te_4$ compound – 7 mol % $TlAs_2Se_4$. In the $TlAs_2Se_4$ - $CuCr_2Te_4$ system, it has been established that during normal cooling based on $TlAs_2Se_4$, the glass formation regions will extend to 12 mol % $CuCr_2Te_4$.

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